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D3.1 CONCEPTUAL RESEARCH PAPER

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List of Abbreviations

DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
ER	Experienced Researcher
ESR	Early-Stage Researcher
NGO	Non-governmental organisation
TalTech	Tallinn University of Technology
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

Deliverable 3.1 (D3.1) is the first deliverable of Work Package 3 - Joint pilot research project on public sector innovation capabilities for digital and sustainable transformations.

In this collaborative deliverable, the partner organizations have successfully crafted a comprehensive research protocol. This protocol outlines the framework, research inquiries, and methodological strategies that shall guide both collective and individual research activities, including co-supervised PhD projects. To ensure widespread acceptance and comprehension, the protocol has been presented at the 45th annual Conference of the European Group for Public Administration (EGPA'23) held in Zagreb, Croatia from 5th to 8th September. This event provided a unique platform for PADST members to showcase the project's initial academic outputs.

The culmination of this concerted effort has yielded two high-level theoretical and conceptual research papers. These papers (submitted for publication to the peer-review journals) offer in-depth exploration of the rapidly evolving paradigms of digital transformation within the global public sector. They also provide critical insights into the intricate relationships between these paradigms and the urgent challenges posed by sustainability.

This initiative represents a significant milestone in advancing knowledge and discourse at the crossroads of public sector digital transformation and sustainability. The outcomes of this deliverable promise to deliver guidance to both academic and professional communities alike.

Research Protocol for Public Sector Digital Transformation and Sustainability: conceptual research papers

1. Government Capacities for Connecting the Sustainability and Digital Transitions A Multilevel Framework for Studying the Twin Transition

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Work in progress, please do not cite or share before the publication

Abstract

Governments across Europe are facing the challenge of shaping the 'twin transition', by adjusting to the digital age in such a way that this induces sustainable development. Sustainability warrants that the quest for satisfying our needs does not compromise the quality of the environment and the ecosystem should be sustained for the sake of future generations. The digital transformation on the other hand, is a fundamental change process enabled by digital technologies that aims to bring radical improvement and innovation in public administration. While there is extensive literature on the sustainable transition and the digital transition, so far limited attention has been paid to the interconnectedness of these transitions. We aim to bring together these different strands of literature in order to understand the nexus between the two and provide a new conceptual understanding. We argue that there is a need for institutional adjustments which require governments to (re)develop capacities to cope with this twin transition. In conceptualizing these actions, we make a distinction between the macro, meso and micro level, resulting in a multilevel framework for shaping the twin transition.

1. Introduction

Two seemingly separate external socio-technical developments – the sustainability transformation and the digital transformation – require governments to build the capacity to respond and lead the way. While these two transitions have often been seen as separate challenges to be handled by different government departments, the interconnectedness of these challenges is increasingly emphasized. Governments across Europe are facing the pressure of fruitfully shaping the 'twin transition', by adjusting to the digital age while inducing sustainable development. The twin transition has been identified as a key area of research by the European Union (Muench et al., 2022). The key message of the report 'Toward a green and digital future' (Muench et al., 2022), is formulated as follows: 'To unlock their potential and to prevent negative effects, the green and digital transitions require a proactive and integrated management.' (Muench et al., 2022: iv). Thus, the authors highlight that capacities – from their perspective: a proactive and integrated management – is needed to make the twin transition work. This paper explores the nature of the interconnectedness of the digital transformation and sustainability and discusses the required government capacities to tackle this challenge.

Both challenges – safeguarding the planet and domesticating technological innovation – have been extensively discussed in separate strands of literature. Sustainability warrants that the quest for satisfying our needs should not compromise the quality of the environment and the ecosystem should be sustained for the sake of future generations (Feroz et al., 2021; Kaswan et al., 2019). Government is seen as a key actor in the sustainability transition and the need to adapt government to be able to realize key transition tasks has been discussed in the literature (Braams et al., 2021).

The digital transformation on the other hand, is a fundamental change process enabled by digital technologies that aims to bring radical improvement and innovation to society (Westerman et al., 2014; Vial, 2019). Specifically for governments, the digital transformation is both an external challenge (Van Dijck, 2020) – how to respond to

new challenges such as exploitation of platform workers, fake news and online attacks? – and an internal challenge – how to use the technologies to strengthen government effectiveness, efficiency and legitimacy (Mergel et al., 2019)?

The academic literature occasionally and often implicitly highlights a variety of different connections between these two transitions (Husain, Sohag & Wu, 2022; Esses, Csete & Németh 2021; Burlacu, Popescu, Diaconu, & Sârbu, 2021). This literature, however, is highly fragmented. Explicit connections are mentioned between the digital transformation and specific forms of sustainability transition such as the decarbonization (Fouquet & Hippe, 2022) and the circular economy (Ortega-Gras et al., 2021). A number of publications, especially on smart cities and smart governance, argue more generally that the digital transformation can provide solutions to support sustainability efforts. For example, big data analytics, social media and AI technologies can help to implement sustainability solutions (Rosário & Dias, 2022). Linkov et al. (2018) discuss some challenges of the twin transition. They stress that big data promises to drive growth and contribute to the realization of the SDGs but creates new types of vulnerabilities for cyber-attacks and power imbalances due to the central position of big tech. In addition, they stress that artificial intelligence provides the promise of better decision-making about sustainability issues but also generates a host of (ethical) risks. Finally, they stress that distributed ledger technologies can help to generate trust among societal actors as a basis for collaboration on sustainability objectives but also generate a variety of risks when these technologies are not correctly governed

To add to this complexity, the link between the sustainability and digital transformations is discussed in the literature at different levels: the institutional, the organizational and the individual levels. At the institutional levels, a growing stream of publications, based on Mazzucato's (2018) seminal work, highlight how global challenges require new government institutions that focus on realizing societal missions (see also: Kattel & Mazzucato, 2018; Hekkert et al., 2020). At the organizational level, new organizational forms for government have been discussed that emphasize the capacity to innovate as basis for responding to the requirements of the twin transitions (Gieske et al., 2016; Bekkers & Tummers, 2018; Meijer, 2019). Finally, at the individual level there is a growing attention for the capacities of individual civil servants to work on innovation and to realize societal missions (Wilson & Mergel, 2022; Dingelstad et al., 2022).

We observe that all kinds of connections are explicitly and implicitly discussed between the sustainability and digital transitions but our conceptual understanding of the relations between the two transitions is fragmented and limited. In addition, the urgency of connecting the transitions is highlighted but, apart from the general key requirements of the European Union (Muench et al., 2022), a thorough understanding of the government capacities that are needed to make the twin transition work is lacking. Therefore, this paper has the ambition (1) to provide a multilevel conceptual understanding of the twin transition and (2) to provide an exploratory overview of the government capacities that are needed to make the twin transition work, and (3) to discuss the connections between the capacities at the different levels.

Key building blocks for the conceptual understanding of the twin transition and the exploratory overview of government capacities are a multilevel framework and the concept 'government capacity'. The multilevel framework is a way of understanding government which has been applied to topics as diverse as transparency (Porumbescu, Meijer & Grimmelikhuijsen, 2022) to healthcare regulation (Øyri & Wiig, 2022), government legitimacy (Bitektine & Haack, 2015) and algorithmic transparency in the public sector (Giest & Grimmelikhuijsen, 2020). Porumbescu et al. (2022:) stress that the multilevel – or layered – approach is insightful since it '(...) enables researchers to capture institutional, organizational and individual dynamics'. They identify the institutional layer (macro), the organizational layer (meso) and the individual layer (micro) as the basic layers for a multilevel framework.

Public sector capacity is sometimes defined from an internal perspective – can the organization realize its objectives? – and sometimes from an external perspective – can the organization realize stakeholder expectations? Polidano, 2000: 808 provides the following internal definition: ‘the ability of an organization to act effectively on a sustained basis in pursuit of its objectives’ whereas Gargan (1981: 652) provides an external definition: ‘the interplay of expectation, resources, and problems’. Combining these two perspectives, we would like to define the public sector capacity as the capacity of the public sector to realize the objectives they have aligned with stakeholders' expectations.

Building upon the multilevel framework, this basic understand of government capacity can be translated into a more fine-grained understand where government capacity consists of (1) the institutional position of government and legitimizing support to fulfill societal expectations (macro), (2) the organizational strategy and operational capacities to translate governmental ambitions into organizational actions and (3) the individual skills and motivations to execute tasks in government organizations (see also the OECD-report by Willems & Baumert (2003) for a similar approach). These three levels will be developed further in the following sections of this paper.

We built the argument in this paper on an analysis of a wide variety of conceptual and empirical papers on the topics of the green and digital transition and their interrelations. In addition, we have also analyzed relevant policy papers such as the already mentioned JRC-report on the twin transition (Muench et al., 2022) and an EU-report about the impact of the twin transition on the labor market and the workplace (Bednorz et al., 2022). We realize that this paper is highly ambitious, and it will certainly not be possible to discuss all relevant research findings, perspectives and angles. Specific empirical research into the twin transition is still scarce and therefore our paper can be regarded as a call for action for more systematic research into the various capacities that are needed to successfully realize this intertwined transition. We hope this paper forms stimulus for researchers around the globe to do rich and pragmatic research into a topic that is very urgent and of great importance to the survival of the planet.

2. Transitions at the institutional level

At the institutional – or macro – level, the key issue is how societal expectations of government are translated into formal and informal institutions and to what extent current institutions can ensure that societal expectations can be met (Porumbescu et al., 2022: 15). There is a focus on paradigmatic changes in the role of government in society: how government institutions need to be fundamentally repositioned to facilitate the sustainability transition (Burns, 2012). The institutional level covers a variety of fundamental topics such as the tasks and responsibilities of government, the form and position of government in society and the mechanisms for democracy and legal traditions and frameworks.

There are few publications that conceptualize public sector capacity at this level. An exception is Polidano (2000) who identifies ‘policy capacity’ and ‘implementation authority’ as two key elements (and ‘operational efficiency’ as a third one but we will position this at the meso level). We will build upon these two elements, reframe ‘implementation authority’ as ‘government legitimacy’ and add the ability to collaborate with other national governments. Thus, the key questions are about the effectiveness – what can government do to tackle societal challenges? –, the legitimacy of government - how it can legitimize its position and approach? – and the global connective capacity (Eilstrup-Sangiovanni & Westerwinter, 2022) – how can government around the world collaborate to respond to global challenges? Therefore, three central capacities can be distinguished: the policy capacity, the legitimizing capacity and the global connective capacity. Government capacities at the institutional level thus require innovative forms of governance. This means changes to the ‘rules of the game’: institutional interactions need to be structured radically

different to ensure that these interactions – the games real actors play (Scharpf, 1997) – indeed contribute to the sustainability and digital transformations.

*Institutional government capacities for the **sustainability transition***

For the sustainability transition, there is a lively discussion on the government capacities that are needed to tackle societal challenges and fulfill societal expectations. Regarding a sustainable planet, there is relative consensus on what the expectations are that need to be fulfilled. In, 1987, the Brundtland Report provided the following definition that is still often used to indicate what the goal is of the sustainability transition: ‘Sustainable Development is the development that satisfies the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.’ (World Commission on Environment and Development, 1987, par. 27).

The government interventions – policy capacity – that are needed for the sustainability transformation are widely debated (for overviews: Kraft, 2017; Russel & Kirsop-Taylor, 2022). These overviews both discuss the variety in key issues (e.g., climate change policies, biodiversity policies) and the various general issues for sustainable development policies (policy integration, policy instruments, collaborative governance). For this paper, we would like to highlight two specific approaches here that have gained much traction in government and academic debates. A key approach for understanding this capacity is transition management (Loorbach, 2010) which highlights how policymakers can shape the sustainability transition. Based on an analysis of many publications on transition management, Braams et al. (2022) have distilled five government tasks: give direction, support governance, support the new, destabilize the unsustainable and develop internal capabilities and structures. The key premise in this literature is that government policies are needed to radically transform current patterns. In parallel, an approach that highlights the need to work in a focused manner on these challenges is mission-oriented innovation (Mazzucato, 2018). This literature emphasizes the need for long-term government commitment and a clear focus. Mazzucato (2018: 810): ‘Missions should be broad enough to engage the public and attract cross-sectoral investment and remain focused enough to involve industry and achieve measurable success. By setting the direction for a solution, missions do not specify how to achieve success. Rather, they stimulate the development of a range of different solutions to achieve the objective. As such, a mission can make a significant and concrete contribution to meeting an Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) or Societal Challenge.’

In addition, there is a debate on the new position of government that is needed to be able to realize the sustainability transformation and how this new position can be legitimized (legitimizing capacity). Various proposals have been made for innovating democracy to enhance its focus on the sustainability transformation which emphasize the role of future generations and of non-human actors (Beckman, 2008; Thompson, 2010; Latour, 2017). The basic problem analysis is that current democratic arrangements emphasize the preferences of current human actors and therefore may not result in broad support for transformation policies. New arrangements could shift the balance and therefore strengthen the legitimacy of transformation policies. Recent work has highlighted the need to develop a new legitimizing rationale for transformative government (Braams et al., 2021). Braams et al. (2021) highlight how we need a new form of government legitimation – transformative government – as a basis for directing the actions and decisions of government at all levels towards the sustainability transformation.

There is also substantive discussion about the type of global collaboration between governments that is needed to realize the sustainability transition (global connective capacity). The key institution is the United Nations and global collaboration is being discussed at United National Climate Change Conferences (COP). The Sustainable Development Goals are an institution created to facilitate these forms of global action and can even be labelled as ‘governance through goals’ (Kanie & Bierman, 2017): the

idea is that jointly formulated goals will help to coordinate the global public and private action that is needed to realize the sustainability transformation.

*Institutional government capacities for the **digital transition***

For the digital transformation, the societal expectations are more debated. In the literature, many undesirable outcomes have been highlighted such as dehumanization (Nissenbaum & Walker, 1998), big tech control (Alford, 2021), misinformation (Fowler-Watt & McDougall, 2022) and massive surveillance (Wood and Monahan, 2019). Various authors warn for technocratic, capitalist or authoritarian dominance as new technologies facilitate new forms of power (Zuboff, 2019; Srivastava, 2021). The dystopian visions dominate the literature but some authors – mostly from engineering – also highlight that the digital transformation plays a key role in realizing a large variety of, sometimes seemingly contradictory, objectives such as economic growth, societal stability, poverty relief and nature conservation (for example: Neugebauer, 2019). In the policy debate, there are still high expectations, and the digital transformation is seen by the EU as the key to tackling a wide variety of challenges (see: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/>).

For some time, there has been a debate about the effectiveness of government policy to influence the digital transformation (policy capacity). The digital transformation is largely shaped by big tech companies and there is much discussion about the ability to regulate these companies (Wörsdörfer, 2020, Moore & Tambini, 2021; Petropoulos, 2021). The recent edited volume by Moore & Tambini (2021) highlights key issues such as enhancing competition, increasing accountability, safeguarding privacy and protecting democracy. The overarching issue, the governance of platforms, is also discussed in fundamental political philosophical terms such as the social contract of platforms with society.

The legitimacy for government interventions is hardly an issue: there is broad societal support for government interventions in the continuously changing digital sector. An indication for the broad support are recent hearings in the United States where both Democrats and Republicans ask hard questions to the tech industry about their contributions to societal welfare and wellbeing. Even for a democratically polarized country such as the US, there is broad consensus that ‘Big Tech has grown too powerful and that action must be taken to address its abuse of power’ (Alford, 2021: 893).

In view of the international competition between big tech companies, there is hardly any global collaboration for the digital transformation. The need for international collaboration on digital transformation has primarily focused on international collaborations such as the European Union and other regional collaborations. An interesting finding from research into the General Data Protection Regulation is that this had an effect on many other countries. This effect has been referred to as the ‘Brussels Effect’ (Gunst & De Ville, 2021) and describes how laws can have an effect across borders through market mechanisms resulting in the globalization of standards. As such, even if there are no global agreements between national governments, there is still the possibility that global standards can be created.

*Institutional government capacities for the **twin transition***

While the literature on the institutional capacities for government is enormous for the two separate transitions, there is a limited number of publications focusing on the institutional capacity for realizing the combination of the two transitions. Medaglia, Misaruca and Aquara (2021) investigated the link between digital government and the sustainable development goals through a systematic literature review and concluded that some relations have been investigated but overall, our academic knowledge on this relation is limited. In a more general review of the link between digitalization and sustainability at the level of nations, Gouvea et al. (2018) show convincing support for a positive relation between a country’s use of information and communication

technologies and its environmental sustainability. Their study, however, does not provide information about how this is related to institutional government capacities.

In the European Union, the need to work on the policy capacity have been highlighted through the recent policy paper on the twin transition (Muench et al., 2022). In parallel, policymakers in the United Nations (UN) and Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) are also examining the original sustainability policy concepts from the Brundtland Report through the lens of digitalization (Linkov et al., 2018). Linkov et al. (2018) develop this idea for the policy capacity further and identify ‘adaptive governance’ as the capacity that is needed for the twin transition or, in their own words, ‘a sustainable digital world’. Adaptive governance is an approach that builds upon three governance approaches – laissez-faire, precautionary and stewardship – and connects these to three digitalization fields – big data, artificial intelligence and distributed ledgers – to realize digital sustainability – defined as economic, social and environmental sustainability. As they formulate it: ‘Given the governing authorities and strategies taken by a given government, adaptability is needed to iteratively address adversarial threats related to digital sustainability as framed by the SDGs’ (Linkov et al., 2018: 6).

We did not find any specific discussion of the legitimacy of governments for working on the twin transition apart from the basic idea that government needs to use the best instruments available to contribute to the realization of the SDGs while minimizing the disruptive effects of these technologies upon social networks and ways of life (Linkov et al., 2018).

Muench et al. (2022) mostly stresses the policy capacity but also highlights the need for a European connective capacity. This point is not mentioned in other publications but a more general argument seems to be relevant here. Specifically for the global connective capacity, a radical change has also been proposed in the literature by Romme et al. (2018) who presents a model for innovating global governance which is generic in nature and could be applied to both transitions. Romme et al. (2018: 152, 153): ‘This so-called United People (UP) model involves a circular hierarchy in which power and communication flow in ways that help the global community to effectively address transnational challenges and problems. It involves several, relatively small, governance bodies—rather than a large parliamentary assembly that tends to cripple responsive decision-making.’

Conclusions

Combining the two sets of expectations, we can characterize the expectations for the twin transitions as an effective and legitimate way to save the planet for both future generations and other forms of life by organizing worldwide collaborations. The capacities that are needed are forms of governance that (1) work effectively quickly since they need to be able to respond to urgent threats and (2) have broad societal support to ensure their legitimacy among different segments of society and (3) enable worldwide collaborations since national governments need to collaborate to be able to fulfill citizen expectations regarding global sustainability.

In the literature we found various proposals that have been developed to strengthen the policy, legitimizing and global connective capacities. Especially for the sustainability transformation, there are fundamental debates that touch upon key institutional foundations of government. None of the proposals for innovating governance, however, has systematically explored how this can be connected to the digital transformation. Thus, new research is needed to explore this nexus by focusing on (1) the policy capacity for realizing the twin transition, (2) the legitimizing capacity for providing support for transformative digital government and (3) the connective capacity to collaborate in international organizations on the twin transitions.

Table 1. Overview of literature at the institutional level

Sustainability	Digital transition	Twin transition
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	transition		
Policy capacity	- Transition management - Mission-oriented innovation	- Regulating big tech	- Adaptive governance
Legitimizing capacity	- Democratic innovation - Transformative government	- Broad societal support for tech regulation	- Contribute to sustainability transition while minimizing negative side effects
Global connective capacity	- Climate Change Conferences - Sustainable Development Goals	- Absent due to international competition - Brussels effect	- Innovating global governance

3. Transitions at the organizational level

The organizational – or meso – level directs our attention to the question of how the societal expectations for the twin transition are shaped in and by organizations (Porumbescu et al., 2022: 27). The key argument is that abstract institutional frameworks do not directly produce decisions and actions that influence people and society; they only do this when they have been translated into organizational policies and practices. This means that this level focuses our attention on the strategic plans of organizations, their systems, personnel policies, operational procedures and collaborations with other organizations. We argue that the actual realization of institutional level ambitions depends on organizational commitment, an operational capacity and the ability to collaborate in the networks.

The literature on the capacity of government organizations to realize objectives is enormous and one of the key foci of attention in the social sciences and builds upon the foundational work by Max Weber on bureaucratic organizations. For the purpose of this paper, we distinguish three types of capacities at the organizational level: the strategic capacity (formulating strategic objectives and plans related to the transition challenges (Poister & Streib, 1995; George, Walker & Monster, 2019)), the operational capacity (translating these strategic plans into organizational practices (Moore, 1995; Polidano, 2000)) and the network capacity (collaborations with other – public, private and societal – organizations to realize strategic objectives (Klijn & Koppenjan, 2015)).

Both for the sustainability and digital transformations, it is important to make a distinction between the internal and external aspects of these transformations. For the digital transformation, a distinction between the digitalization of government and the regulation of the digitalization of society is crucial. Specifically for algorithms, for example, Lorenz et al. (2022) make a distinction between regulation of (i.e. regulating the use of algorithms by companies and other organizations in society) and regulation with algorithms ((i.e. using algorithms to improve the work of the regulator). In general, the internal aspect refers to the realization of these transformations in the (green and digital) organizations. The external aspect entails the regulation and steering of these transformation in society.

*Organizational government capacities for the **sustainability transition***

As for the internal aspects of the sustainability transformation, there is a growing discussion on sustainable organizations and this discussion mostly focuses on how organizations can reduce their own environmental costs. The focus is only on

operational capacities. There is little attention for strategic capacities and, as this is about the internal aspect, network capacity does not play a role. The literature on green organizations is mostly generic in nature (Green et al., 2000) and, as far as we could find, few publications specifically focus on government organizations. Some studies focus on the topic of government procurement (Blome et al., 2014; Vejaratnam et al., 2020). Adams et al (2014) focus on the use of sustainable performance measures in the public sector as an operational activity. Green et al. (2000) analyze both public and private sector organizations and emphasize the need for organizations to focus on environmental sustainability in their purchasing, consumption and innovation. Overall, however, the green organization is an organization that focuses on low use of energy, limited use of resources, a focus on recycling, limiting food waste, etc. For these efforts, there are no differences between public and private organizations.

For the external aspect of the sustainability transformation, this is not so different. A whole body of literature addresses what government needs to do to contribute to the sustainable transition by stimulating innovation and collaborating with a variety of profit and non-profit organizations, but no publications specifically address what this means in terms of strategic, operational and network capacities of government organizations.

*Organizational government capacities for the **digital transition***

As for the internal aspect of the digital transition, there is a substantive body of literature on digital government organizations and this literature is rapidly expanding. Key foundational work includes Snellen & Van de Donk (1998, 'public administration in an information age'), Fountain (2001, 'building the virtual state') & Dunleavy & Margetts (2006, 'digital era governance'). These analyses all highlight that the use of digital technologies is not only an instrument for government organizations but transforms their very nature. Building upon classic work in the field of digital government studies, on more recent literature and on empirical research through expert interviews, Mergel et al. (2019: 12) provide the following comprehensive definition of digital transformation:

'Digital transformation is a holistic effort to revise core processes and services of government beyond the traditional digitization efforts. It evolves along a continuum of transition from analog to digital to a full stack review of policies, current processes, and user needs and results in a complete revision of the existing and the creation of new digital services. The outcome of digital transformation efforts focuses among others on the satisfaction of user needs, new forms of service delivery, and the expansion of the user base.'

As the digital transformation is a socio-technical transformation, Mergel et al. (2019) identify a change in culture, skills and mindset as a key condition to make digital transformation last.

Both in the more classic publications on the topic (Snellen & Van de Donk, 1998; Fountain, 2001; Dunleavy et al., 2006) and in recent literature, the three dimensions of organizational capacity are addressed. The need to have a digital government strategy is emphasized in the volume edited by Sandoval-Almazán et al. (2017). For the operational capacity, there is attention for the realization of digital government but also for newer forms such as 'agile government' (Mergel et al., 2018), 'mobile government' (Ntaliani et al., 2008), and 'algorithmic government' (Gupta & Pal, 2021). The network capacity was already addressed by Homburg's (1999) focus on 'interorganizational information systems' and continues to receive attention through 'e-governance' (Dawes, 2008), 'collaborative e-government' (Ae Chun et al., 2012), and 'open governance' (Meijer et al., 2019).

The external aspect, the organizational capacities needed for regulating the digital transformation of society, has focused primarily on market regulation and privacy regulation. Market regulators have been working hard on ensuring proper forms of

market oversight in the age of platform organizations and Big Tech. Privacy commissioners in many countries play a key role in ensuring that public and private organizations follow privacy rules. For both forms of regulation, however, no studies have systematically the organizational capacities that are needed to fulfill these roles adequately. Currently there is quite a bit of attention for the regulation of algorithms (Lorenz et al., 2022). The focus, however, is again very much on normative and legal issues and no information is available on organizational capacities.

*Organizational government capacities for the **twin transition***

For the internal aspect of the twin transition, greening the use of information and communication technologies used by government organizations, societal and academic attention is on the rise. At the moment, the concept of 'Green IT' has been developed mostly for private sector organizations (Malhotra et al., 2013; Darshana et al., 2017) and 'Green E-Governance' has not yet been addressed. At the same time, the literature on 'Green IT' seems highly relevant for public sector organizations as it addresses general issues such as reducing energy usage of data storage and recycling hardware.

A more generic body of literature that provides a basis for both the organizational capacity for the sustainability transformation and the digital transformation is the literature on public sector innovation. Important work by Kattel et al. (2022) emphasizes that innovation – referring to Mazzucato's entrepreneurial state – requires a string bureaucracy. They emphasize that drive innovation, shape markets and steer inclusive green innovation. Government bureaucracy need the strategic and operational capacities to stimulate innovation. In addition, Bason (2010) highlights that organizational commitment to making radical changes depends on the ability to stimulate and realize continuous innovation. Bason (2010: 71 – 86) explicitly discusses that an innovation strategy highlights how an organization wants to work with innovation and indicates that organizations can choose between four different strategies: entrepreneurial innovation, institutional innovation, open innovation and strategic-reflexive innovation.

The various publications on the public innovation capacity are relevant for understanding the operational capacity for the twin transition. Gieske et al. (2016) discuss the ambidexterity of public innovation: the need to both develop creative new ideas but also turn these ideas into actual practices. Building upon this notion and also on evolutionary models of innovation, Meijer (2019) distinguishes five components of the public innovation capacity: mobilizing, experimenting, institutionalizing, balancing and coordinating.

For the network capacity, the literature on collaborative innovation is specifically relevant. Sorensen & Torfing (2012) combine the literatures on collaborative governance and public innovation and indicate how collaborative innovation can be a way to shape the development and implementation of new innovative approach in networks of public and private organizations. Hartley et al. (2013) build upon this work and discuss various types of collaborative innovation such as public-private networks, governance networks, public-private innovation partnerships and crowdsourcing. Hartley et al. (2013: 826) indicate: '(...) collaboration can open up innovation processes for the active participation of a broad range of actors with different innovation assets.'

Conclusions

In sum, at the organizational level there is a distinction between the changes in the organization – green and digital organizations – and the changes in the role of the organizations in society – regulating and steering the sustainability and digital transformation. Both require strategic, operational and network capacities. Finally, there is no literature on the twin transition at the organizational level but general literature on public sector innovation seems directly relevant. This results in the following overview (Table 2).

Table 2. Overview of literature at the organizational level

	Sustainability transition	Digital transition	Twin transition (generic notions)
Strategic capacity			
Internal	-	- Digital strategy formulation	- Strategic innovation plans - Creative bureaucracy
External	-	- Digital market and society strategy	- Strategic collaborative innovation plans
Operational capacity			
Internal	- Green organizations	- Digital government - Agile government - Mobile government - Algorithmic government	- Public innovation capacity
External	- Regulatory capacity - Innovation capacity	- Regulatory capacity	- Collaborative innovation capacity
Network capacity			
	-	- Interorganizational information systems - E-governance - Collaborative e-government - Open governance	- Collaborative innovation

4. Transitions at the civil servant level

At the individual – or micro – level, the focus is on the perceptions, attitudes and behavioral responses of individuals in public organizations that need to do the work to realize the twin transition (Porumbescu et al., 2022: 14, 15). Crucial to this perspective is that there is a cognitive dimension (seeing and understanding the interconnectedness of the two transitions), an attitude dimension (realizing and acknowledging the importance of this connection) and a behavioral dimension (doing the twin transition work).

*Civil servant capacities for the **sustainability transition***

The strategic skills of civil servants for realizing the sustainability transition are discussed in empirical studies by Braams et al. (2023). They emphasize that civil servants need to have the organizational astuteness to react to contestation of efforts to realize the sustainability transition and to be able to drive the transition forward.

The attitude of civil servants towards the sustainability transformation is addressed in a study by Stritch & Christensen (2014) on the link between organizational commitment and public service motives and public employees' workplace eco-initiatives. On the basis of a study in a large city in the US, they find that connectedness to nature, organizational commitment, and public service motivation are significant predictors of eco-initiative in the public workplace. In addition, Alzgoool

(2019) stresses that green HRM – human resource management directed at stimulating green behavior – plays an important role in stimulating employees to have a positive attitude towards green values.

A stream of publications address the question of employee green behavior (EGB) and how this can be stimulated. Ones and Dilchert (2012) identify with five categories of EGB: (1) working sustainably, (2) conserving resources, (3) influencing others, (4) taking initiative, and (5) avoiding harm. Unsworth et al. (2021) present a theoretical analysis of Employee Green Behavior (EGB) and stress that this is shaped by an interaction between individual and organizational factors. Since not all individuals have the same attitude towards environmental sustainability, a diversity in approaches is needed to stimulate the various employees. To stimulate EGB, Green HRM is increasingly discussed in the literature. Rani & Mishra (2014: 3633: ‘Green HRM means using every employee interface in such a manner in order to promote and maintain sustainable business practices as well as creating awareness, which in turn, helps organizations to operate in an environmentally sustainable fashion.’

*Civil servant capacities for the **digital transition***

For the digital transition, there is a longer tradition of research into the digital skills of civil servants (Schuppan, 2010; Van Deursen & Van Dijk, 2010; Casalino et al., 2020). This research highlights the need for civil servants to understand new technologies, to appreciate its potential and to be able to effectively use new technologies for their work. While much of this work focus on ‘digital literacy’, there is a growing emphasis on the idea the ‘digital literacy’ needs to be contextualized and connected to the work of civil servants. Recently, interesting work has been done by Dingelstad et al (2022) on data competences which emphasizes that digital competences need to be connected to administrative competences. They refer to the requires skills as ‘hybrid data competences’.

Attitude is often, in line with theories on the adoption of innovation, conceptualized as the willingness to use digital technologies. There are some studies available about the attitude of civil servants towards specific forms of digitalization. Alomar (2023) analyzes the determinants of the attitude of civil servants toward using e-public procurement and finds that six factors have a significant impact on the attitude of civil servants, namely perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, training, resources, position of the hierarchy, and clients' attitude. Kleiman et al. (2023) study civil servants willingness to using open data and find that social influences, performance expectancy, data management knowledge and risks have a significant influence.

In terms of the practices of the digital transformation, the actual behavior, we could not find any studies.

*Civil servant capacities for the **twin transition***

As far as we could find, no work exists that explores the individual capacities needed for realizing the twin transition. At the same time, more general notions about capacities of civil servants can form a basis for analyzing the individual capacities.

A key argument from the literature is that individual servants do not need to have all the capacities related to the two transitions but they should be able to forge fruitful connections at the individual level. Schot et al. (2000) refer to this as collaborative professionalism: professionals should not only master their own field but also be able to connect their field to other fields. This can mean that digital experts need to acquire the capacity to work with sustainability experts when making technological choices about digital technology.

In addition, Kattel et al. (2022) emphasize that civil servants sometimes need to be ‘bureaucracy hackers’ who revolutionize government organizations from the inside by not following rules and creating room for innovation.

Table 3. Overview of literature at the individual level

	Sustainability transition	Digital transition	Twin transition (generic notions)
Skill capacity	- Strategic organizational skills	- Hybrid data competences	- Collaborative professionalism - Bureaucracy hackers
Attitudinal capacity	- Green HRM to stimulate green values	- Intention to use technology (based on social norms,	-
Behavioral capacity	- Employee Green Behavior (EGB) -Green HRM stimulates UGB	-	-

5. Toward a multilevel framework for studying the twin transition

The three different levels of the twin transition have now been discussed for each level and we have conceptualized the various government capacities for the twin transition. Figure 1 highlights how the two transitions are separate but also interconnected, how legitimate and effective government action to guide the twin transition requires policy, legitimizing and international connective capacity, how the new position of government in society requires a strategic capacity of government organizations, an operational capacity and a network capacity, and how individual skills and attitude – skills capacity and attitudinal capacity – are needed as a basis for organizational capacity.

Figure 1. Overview of government capacities for the twin transitions

In our exploration of the literature, we noted that, at the institutional level, the literature on the sustainability transformation is more expansive than the literature on the digital transformation. At the same time, the literature on the digital transformation is more expansive than the literature on the sustainability transformation at the organizational level. In the literature in public administration studies, the sustainability transformation is often more viewed as a societal transformation which requires organizational action whereas the digital transformation is widely seen as an organizational transformation with societal implications.

On the basis of our exploration of the literature on the sustainability and digitalization transformation and on the very limited literature that discusses the intersection and more general literature, we have identified a conceptual understanding of capacities for the twin transition at each of these levels (see Table 4). We have argued that our academic understanding is still limited and much research is needed to understand these key issues that the different levels.

So far, we have not yet focused on the interconnections between the levels and, as far as we know, no research has yet been conducted on these interfaces. For this reason, we have added points at the interface between the levels to complete our multi-level model of government capacities for the twin transition.

For the interface between the institutional and the organizational levels (macro-meso), we can formulate interfaces in two directions:

- 2.1. Translating institutional changes to requirements for government organizations
- 2.2. Facilitating contributions from innovative organizations to institutional changes

And for the interface between the organizational and the individual levels (meso-micro), we can formulate interfaces in two directions:

- 4.1. Translation of organizational transformation to new sets of individual competences
- 4.2. Organizational conditions for building upon changing individual competences

Finally, one theme can be identified that run through the different levels: leadership. Different forms of political, organizational and individual leadership are needed to work on the required changes at the different levels. As Selznick (1957) has shown, leadership is crucial for changing the fundamental nature of a social system and infuse new values. The literature on leadership and transformation is rich and can form a basis for further understanding how leadership at different levels is needed to shape the competences for the twin transition.

6.1. Institutional, organizational and individual leadership

To summarize the main line of argument, an overview of conceptual framework of government competences for the twin transition is presented in Table 4:

Table 4. Conceptual framework of government competences for the twin transition

<i>Level/Interface</i>	<i>Items</i>
Institutional level (macro)	1.1. Policy capacity for the twin transition 1.2. Legitimizing capacity for the twin transition 1.3. Connective global capacity for the twin transition
Interface macro-meso	2.1. Institutional changes → organizational requirements 2.2. Innovative organizations → institutional changes
Organizational level (meso)	3.1. Strategic organizational capacity for the twin transition 3.2. Operational organizational capacity for the twin transition 3.3. Organizational network capacity for the twin transition
Interface meso-micro	4.1. Organizational transformation → individual competences

	4.2. Individual competences → organizational transformation
Individual level (micro)	5.1. Skill capacity for the twin transition 5.2. Attitudinal capacity for the twin transition 5.3. Behavioral capacity for the twin transition
Cross-cutting theme	6.1. Institutional, organizational and individual leadership

6. Conclusions: research agenda for studying the twin transition

The argument that we make in this paper that developing an academic understanding of the twin transitions requires us to zoom in on micro-level changes and zoom out to position these changes in the context of organizational and societal changes. The model we developed in this paper is general in its conceptualization of government capacity and can be applied to other societal challenges. As such, it connects to broader debates about the need for government innovation as a basis for tackling societal challenges (Bason, 2010; Mazzucato, 2018; Hekkert et al., 2020). We discussed it specifically for the twin transitions to identify knowledge gaps and present a research agenda for investigating the twin transitions.

On the basis of our analysis, we would like to highlight the following topics for further research:

1. *Measuring government capacities for the twin transition.* Our paper provides a conceptual overview but does not indicate how the different dimension of the government capacities can be measured. Building upon previous work at the different levels, instruments can be developed to measure the capacities at the macro, meso and micro levels.
2. *Understanding determinants of government capacities for the twin transition.* Through comparative research, differences between government capacities for the twin transition can be mapped and then determinants for these differences (such as democratic system, GDP, leadership, etc.) can be analyzed.
3. *Methods for strengthening the government capacities for the twin transition.* In addition to an understanding of the determinants, methods for strengthening these capacities through smart allocation of funding, collaborative networks, international learning, etc, can be explored and assessed.
4. *Assessing the impact of the capacities on the realization of the twin transition.* The impact of the competences on the realization of the twin transition can be analyzed to obtain an understanding of which types of competences are crucial and which types of competences work best in different contexts.

In view of the urgency of these issues, we argue for forms of activist research that does not study the various topics from a 'neutral outsider' position but from the perspective of an engaged researcher that aims to make concrete contributions to the different challenges facing governments. There is little time to stop global warming and the various capacities that we have discussed need to be strengthened on a short term to curb this process. Researchers can provide training and evaluate how this training contributes to the micro-level capacity, they can give organizational or government advice and also evaluate how this impacts meso- and macro-level competences. Researchers can work in international networks to facilitates the interchange of knowledge between countries and contribute to global competences for the twin transition. We hope that the framework we provided in this paper will help to facilitate an international research agenda so that we as a research community can contribute to the urgent actions that are needed to realize the twin transition in such a way that we can save our planet.

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2. Dynamic capabilities for transformative policies

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Work in progress, please do not cite or share before the publication.

Introduction

In most mainstream treatments, the challenges of sustainable development and more specifically sustainability transformations tend to be looked through the lens of innovation: complex societal challenges require different forms of innovations (from technological to social and institutional) that can ideally also provide new avenues for broader socio-economic development. This gives modern day innovation debates a clear demand and direction. There is also a growing consensus among academics that this *normative turn* in innovation policy - i.e. toward more directed (Bergek et al. 2023), mission-oriented (Mazzucato 2018), or transformative innovation policy (Schot and Steinmueller 2018; Diercks et al. 2019) - requires also significant rethinking of public sector policy and administrative capacities (e.g. Mazzucato and Kattel 2018; Kattel 2022).

There seems to be also a broader consensus among (innovation) policy scholars that collaborative, iterative, co-creative and experimental forms of governance, policy-making and policy delivery are superior to more traditional forms to achieve the transformative goals, such as tackling climate change (e.g. Karo and Kattel 2018a; McClaren and Kattel 2022; Sabel and Victor 2022; Trischler et al. 2022). Public administration (PA) scholars, entering these debates, have conceptualized this as the need for *transformative government* substituting constitutional and discretionary traditions with more collaborative principles (Braams et al. 2021).

Yet, the current framing of this consensus is only emerging and reminds us of the old “Moon and the Ghetto” insights by Richard Nelson (1977) regarding our limited knowledge and capacities to tackle emergent complex challenges based on our existing/legacy knowledge and governance silos (i.e. in finance, policy, technology). Indeed, we argue that we seem to be at the midst of a necessary *epistemic turn* in innovation policy governance to support the broadly legitimate normative turn. Co-creation, design thinking, experimentation and other concepts around governing transformative innovation processes have one common trait - delegation of expertise to open-ended participatory processes - which reflects our profound uncertainties and ongoing search regarding the right (governance) path forward. Or, we could interpret this as an attempt to introduce collective (entrepreneurship-like) creativity into public sector routines (see Teece 2022 for discussions in the private sector context).

Yet, all of these conceptual approaches for improving policy interventions tend to assume that once better policy interventions are co-created or co-discovered jointly by a diverse set of actors, implementation and delivery become the easier task as these solutions should be based on more legitimate grounds and lead to much easier necessary changes in delivery and implementation practices. But this can be a dangerous simplification by scholars and policy communities - public sector organizations and processes are characterized by path dependencies, legacies, and routine lock-ins, especially if the policy feedback loops are punctuated and complex (Karo and Kattel 2018b).

In this paper, we are explicitly interested in a ‘realist’ perspective on delivering the normative turn of innovation policy. We ask conceptually - through literature review and merging of innovation policy and public administration debates - what it takes from governments, in terms of rethinking policy and administrative processes and capacities, to deliver the desired normative turn in innovation policy.

We argue that the choice of appropriate methods for the necessary co-creative search and selection of appropriate policy mixes depends on *problem-context-method* fit, i.e. new policy models and specific methods and interventions need to fit the types of problems and overarching context of policy and administrative cultures, or traditions. Further, we argue that by merging these streams of literature, it becomes evident that current framings lack sufficient detail and depth on substantiating and operationalizing some of the crucial elements of the desired transformative changes, especially elements related to regime *destabilization* (see Elzinga et al. 2023) that are crucial for speeding-up transformations needed to achieve sustainability goals.

Arguably, much of the institutional and administrative frameworks that modern governments rests upon are built with stability in mind. Concepts such as rule of law, checks-and-balances, administrative neutrality, to name just a handful of them, aim to provide long-term stability for governing societies. Furthermore, for long periods of modern political history, transformative government would have been equated with revolutions and thus particularly in political philosophy we have historically numerous debates and treaties on how to avoid revolutions, or transformations. Max Weber would not be a fan of transformative government.

In the second part of this paper, we propose a research protocol for exploratory analysis of how certain specific units (countries, cities, ministries) try to build capacities and especially *dynamic capabilities* for enabling such key elements of transformations.

Public administration capacities and transformative changes

Public administration scholarship has evolved in recent decades mostly in the context of the new institutionalist school of thought (see e.g. Peters 2019) emphasizing stability, continuity and incrementalism in PA developments (Pollitt 2008). In this context, public sector capacities tend to be operationalized and studied on generic/institutionalist levels of state, policy, and administrative capacities (Painter and Pierre 2004). There have been of course attempts to take this line of analysis further and bring institutional lenses down to the organizational and individual levels of capabilities for different types of policy tasks (e.g. analysis, operations, politics) (see Wu et al. 2015; 2018; as well as Borrás et al. 2023 for a recent literature review).

Yet, most of these framings largely assume that policy making and implementation is a largely rational (expertise and evidence-driven) and structured process happening in the broader institutional context. There have been a few empirical studies highlighting that the reality of policy design and implementation is often not so rational and behind the rational-looking front-stage of policy-making, the backstage of policy-making and implementation might look very different as power plays, capabilities development, sensemaking and other concerns come to play (see van der Steen and van Twist 2018). While the recognition of non-rational logic of policy making is nothing new (e.g. Weber originally argued that most significant changes in the way modern societies function are based on non-rational grounds, such as charismatic authority - see Weber 2019), it has been hard to fit into modern day assumptions of rationality and evidence-based policy-making and public sector reforms.

The currently dominant and most fashionable way to rectify this limitation has been to introduce “public sector innovation” (and the related “innovative” methodologies from design thinking to co-creation) as a positive case of such “non-rational” ways of change and evolution in PA (see Kattel 2015). Over the last decades, there has been a significant convergence between public and private sector modes of innovative management thinking, but also in the way we try to use the concept of innovation for tackling challenges modern day organizations and societies face (see Kattel et al. 2022, 2023). In this context, we also see increasing attempts to conceptualize public

sector capacities and capabilities for tackling modern-day challenges, i.e. from the perspective of problem-oriented governance (Mayne et al. 2020) to specific innovation-oriented public sector capabilities in the punctuated feedback context of public sectors (Karo and Kattel 2018b) as well as public sector dynamic capabilities (Kattel 2022).

One of the common weaknesses of these strands of thinking has been that although they often bring out new elements and lenses on how we should think of capacities and capabilities, they still build on existing incrementalist lines of thinking and operationalize capacities and capabilities building on existing streams of research, conceptualizations and findings. This research is then applied to contexts and challenges - such as transformations towards sustainability - which are quite different from the previous contexts and even from the innovation discourses that have enabled PA to break somewhat with the dominant incrementalist lines.

Namely, even the discussions around the concept of innovation and dynamic capabilities have focused on how organizations 'sense' and 'seize' *new* opportunities (for development) through 'transforming' their own internal routines (see Teece et al. 1997 for original take). Yet, it is increasingly understood that complex and transformative challenges such as sustainability transitions require a more complex approach that does not focus only on recognizing the need and potential for new actions and internal capabilities, but also, at least in the context of public policies, needs to deal also with terminating the unsustainable practices causing the need for new actions in the first place (e.g. see Kanger et al. 2020; Elzinga et al. 2023). We argue that this is the context where most of our incrementalist and cumulative thinking on public sector capacities and capabilities might run into the ground without having the full set of answers and framings.

In this context, Elzinga et al. (2023) have summarized the thinking of sustainability transitions research by differentiating between the necessary *innovation functions* (knowledge development and diffusion, entrepreneurial experimentation, market creation, resource mobilization, legitimation) and *destabilization functions* (unlearning, break-down of knowledge networks, restricting experimentation, market destabilization, resource withdrawal, challenging status quo) underpinned by generic *programmatic functions* (problem and solution directionality, coordination). The traditional innovation policy research has clearly focused on building rationales, intervention logics and capacity elements for the innovation and generic programmatic functions while leaving the destabilization functions largely untouched (see Weber and Rochrachter 2012).

Borras et al. (2023) show in their literature review that the thinking around the various roles of public sector organization in sustainability transitions recognizes the importance of disruption (next to creation and maintenance) as a significant amount of literature discusses - but as the prescriptive task, rather than empirical reality - the role of public sector in disruptive changes (as designer, initiator, facilitator, promoter, opportunist, promoter). It seems from the emergent literature that the destabilization functions should largely follow similar rationales and logic for policy making than innovation functions (e.g. through knowledge-creation, regulations, institution building, budgetary processes - see Elzinga et al. 2023).

This has been translated into actual policy practice through regulatory principles such as "do no significant harm", or concepts such as "green industrial policy". Yet, innovation scholarship itself has recognized that tackling complex challenges in legacy sectors characterized by incumbent interests, power-relations, and institutional advantages is often much more complicated and time-consuming than the experiences of more innovative novelty sectors have made us assume (see Bonvillian and Weiss 2015). We can assume that systemic approaches to transformations that try to coordinate between innovation and destabilization functions and interventions are

currently an exception rather than norm, especially in the context of sustainability challenges (see e.g. Cullenward and Victor 2020, Sabel and Victor 2022 highlighting a few examples of working systems and solutions).

As one explanation to this limitation, Braams et al. (2021) conceptualize that the predominant PA paradigms/traditions (constitutional, discretionary, collaborative) are not really well equipped to deal with the functions/tasks designated to policy and bureaucracy by sustainability transformations frameworks (give direction, support governance, support the new, destabilize the unsustainable, develop internal capabilities). While the collaborative tradition may be most compatible with the sustainability transformations expectations, it falls short exactly regarding the tasks of legitimization of directionality and destabilization (these are clearly the most political, but also tasks/functions politicians are unlikely to pursue). Braams et al. (2022) further validate these claims based on interviews with civil servants from one of the more collaboration-oriented governance systems, the Netherlands.

Hence, these issues seem to be the key areas for developing and pursuing conceptual and empirical research on PA capacities and to rethink existing sustainability-oriented innovation and governance practices. But more critically, we can also take this as a broader critique of the rationalist-incrementalist research traditions in PA, i.e. we have a tendency to look at and measure known principles and institutions of good administration (as codified in traditional public management acronyms, such as POSDCORB by Gulick and Urwick 1937) - or commonly studies and compared PA reform trajectories and models (see Pollitt and Bouckaert 2017). At the same time, management scholars (i.e. Mintzberg 2009) remind us that daily chores of management seem to be very different from text-book level good practices and syntheses and this may be especially so when managers face the demands for innovation and tackling complex challenges (Teece 2022).

In sum, we may be facing another “moon and ghetto” moment (see Nelson 1977) in public administration and public policy thinking: while PA discourses have been gradually incorporating technology and innovation modalities into its frameworks (see Pollitt 2010; 2012, Karo and Kattel 2016a, 2018b; Meijer (2019), the sustainability related transformative changes may require adding additional lenses to include also biodiversity, social equity/just transition related concerns as well as the above-discussed transformative change management related questions: **how to combine routine delivery, dynamic innovation and conflictual destabilization practices and capabilities in PA?**

Dynamic capabilities for managing transformative changes

We propose that the theoretical and conceptual model of dynamic capabilities - specifically designed to integrate routine and entrepreneurial dynamics of organizations (see Teece 2022) - is a useful approach to further the conceptual thinking on PA capacities and capabilities for transformative changes. The usefulness of the approach stems explicitly from its dynamic notions compared to the traditional (neo-) institutionalist approaches to public sector developments.

But given the above review, we argue that we need to advance this line of research from two perspectives:

- a) conceptualizing dynamic capabilities in the context of *destabilization functions*
- b) *exploratory understanding* of how these capabilities are formed and practices in real-life settings (i.e. what are the destabilization routines)

Previously, Karo and Kattel (2018b) have conceptualized public sector innovation

capacities by distinguishing ordinary policy implementation and innovation related routines making the bigger argument that tackling complex societal challenges requires public sector agile stability (Kattel et al. 2022) and organizational variety (Karo and Kattel 2016b). Further, Kattel (2022) has translated the private sector concept of dynamic capabilities (based on sensing, seizing and transforming as entrepreneurial tasks) into PA context and highlights that public sector dynamic capabilities are underpinned by 3 sets of routines:

- *Sense-making routines*: analytical, assessment, information-gathering and processing routines that enable new learning, appraisal and evaluation patterns. These routines can relate to analysing outputs and outcomes (value), as well as the internal performance of an organisation.
- *Connecting routines*: networking and boundary-spanning routines that enable new networks and coalitions of internal and/or external stakeholders to be built. The routines help to (re-)build legitimacy and buy-in for new solutions.
- *Shaping routines*: routines to design and implement specific new directionality for an organisation or policy area, embed and mainstream new solutions into long-term routines, either in policy or in management, and be able to provide resources and support for new initiatives.

We conjecture that the specificities of transformative changes and especially that of destabilization functions require public sector organization to build an additional layer of ***transformation routines***: systems-thinking and change-management routines that link new insights (from sense-making routines) and directionalities (from connecting and shaping routines) with organizational and policy legacies and focus on coordinating phasing-out of old and phasing-in of new practices and solutions.

To give an example of the latter, Sabel and Victor (2022) have introduced the concept of *experimentalist governance* that precisely combines experimentalist organizational and strategic principles (or routines) with experimentalist incentives (especially “penalty defaults”, or credible regulatory exits targeted into foreseeable future in a way that will motivate at least a few actors in a sector to co-search for new solutions) and just transition mechanisms (for the incumbents). This combined theoretical model - adjusted in practice to different problem-solution-contexts (from global agreements on ozone layer protection to agricultural and green energy practices in different countries) - provides an overarching theory and model for transformation in the context of high uncertainty. Still, how these routines (would) work in practice is currently highly under-researched.

Towards a research strategy and design to study public administration capacities and capabilities for sustainability transformations

While there is a booming and growing scene of scholarship attempting to conceptualize and advance the thinking of *what* capacities - mostly discussed on the level of policy capacities - are needed for sustainability oriented transformations (see Borrás et al. 2023; Laranja and Hugo 2023), we claim that there is unfilled gap in research that should look at *how* these capacities are created, legitimized and executed by public sector organizations. Looking at the empirical realities might reveal contextual differences regarding how different countries and systems as well as policy domains tackle the transformative challenges. Furthermore, detailed analysis of transformation processes - such as exit from fossil fuel usage - can reveal also differences in how these capacities are created, legitimized and executed for particular types of interventions/actions/functions (e.g. innovation, destabilization, maintenance).

To simplify the empirical inquiry and research strategies, one can unpack the capacity challenges on 3 layers (here we use the example of the destabilization function) of potential actions through which destabilization processes (in the sense of e.g. unlearning, break-down of knowledge networks, restricting experimentation, market destabilization, resource withdrawal, challenging status quo) could be triggered and executed:

- 1) *state/political capacity* - the overall legitimacy and political attempts to pursue destabilization (e.g. political statements and actions to exit from certain activities and substitute these with more sustainable alternatives)
- 2) *policy capacity* - public policy design and strategy-making level attempts to to pursue destabilization (e.g. technocratic rationales, missions and other policy initiatives to trigger exit from certain activities and substitute these with more sustainable alternatives)
- 3) *administrative capacity* - policy implementation level attempts to pursue destabilization (e.g. either through execution of new political and policy delivered mandates for destabilization or using existing mandates and roles - e.g. novel interpretations of existing policies, regulations - to pursue destabilization).

The conflictual nature of the destabilization processes - which make the particular change processes transformative - mandates that the analysis uses dynamic and open-ended frameworks such as that of dynamic capabilities as it allows for exploratory analysis of the search and selection (or not) of functioning pathways in specific contexts.

Each of these levels can be unpacked and analyzed through the roles, resources and skills of key actors as proposed by Borrás et al. (2023) to understand how different actors contribute (or not) to the formation for dynamic capabilities and overall transformative capacity:

The empirical cases to be analyze need to be indeed transformative in nature, i.e. there has been or is ongoing and explicit political, policy or administrative execution of a transformative change process.

An example of such transformative process could be the ongoing energy transition in Estonia (exit from the use of oil shale in energy production by 2030 through support of

renewable energy investments and just transition policies). The analysis can focus on the specific levels of potential capacity formation, e.g. how has the political mandate to exit from oil shale through development of new innovative energy sources been formalized and executed through the roles, skills, resources and actions of actors on the different levels and what particular roles, actions and skills form the dynamic transformation routines and transformative capacities.

Looking at the existing research on this particular case, Sillak and Vasser (2023) show that co-creation methods - that are part of the collaborative tradition in PA - seem to work better on the policy-making level (drafting energy transition strategies etc) and less so on the level of actual policy implementation and delivery. Or in other words, co-creation practices may enable sense-making and connecting routines, but this does not necessarily mean translation into shaping and transformative routines. How these routines and capacities get formed needs to be further researched, but we are more likely to see political and policy level 'lip service' to transformative changes while the actual implementation of the transformation may be left to more administrative levels and functions (e.g. denial of extraction permits, enforcements of environmental standards etc).

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